

THE PROMISE OF RESTORATIVE JUSTICE: IMPACTS OF AN EDUCATIONAL
EXPERIENCE ON STUDENTS VALUES

by

Emalie Benitez

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Approved by:

Date:

Alissa Ackerman

12/16/2021

Dr. Alissa Ackerman, Department of Criminal Justice

Yuying Tsong

1/4/2022

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Interim Director University Honors Program

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Emalie Benitez

Advisor: Alissa Ackerman, Ph.D.

Department of Criminal Justice, California State University

ABSTRACT Restorative justice is a process that address conflict and crime through the values of, respect, honesty, accountability, vulnerability, and empowerment. This process gives the person who caused harm and the person who was harmed the opportunity to come together to discuss outcomes while, honoring the humanity of all people. My Honors Project focuses on how a restorative justice course shifts ideas about justice, punishment, and personal beliefs. The data illustrates that learning about restorative justice in a sixteen-week course through lectures, discussions, and activities will influence students' perception on empathy, forgiveness, punishment, and social connectedness. The goal of my project is to encourage my readers and audience to view restorative justice as a resolution in our criminal justice system.

Key Words: *Restorative justice, criminal justice system, crime, justice, humanity*

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Background: Restorative Justice

Restorative justice is a process that involves, to the extent possible, those who have a stake in an offense and to collectively identify and address harms, needs and obligations, in order to heal and put things right as possible (Zehr, 2015). In restorative justice, the humanity of all people is being honored. Restorative justice allows a person who has caused harm to understand the damage they have caused to another individual and the people close to that individual. It will enable the person who caused harm to repair the damage they brought to the person who they harmed and the community. Restorative justice holds the person who caused harm accountable for their crimes and gives them the chance to amend themselves. Most importantly, it can bring healing to the person who was harmed, the person who caused harm, and the community.

Restorative Justice can be used in the pre-sentence, post-conviction, or it can also be used with cases that have never been reported. When a horrific crime occurs, the person who was harmed can never express their pain, thoughts, emotions, and questions to the person who caused them harm. However, restorative justice allows the person who was harmed to have a one-on-one conversation with the person who caused them harm. It allows the person who was harmed voice to be heard. Restorative justice is a positive, impactful, and helpful approach in the criminal justice system.

A person who was harmed stated that the restorative justice process "allowed me to be heard and, overall, the process provided a great deal of support and stopped me channeling my anger into total destructiveness" (Bergseth & Bouffard, 2013). Restorative justice views crime as

a violation of human relationships rather than a law violation. Restorative justice focuses on the person who caused harm and the person who was harmed. It focuses on the humanity of all people. Restorative justice sees the person who caused harm and the person who was harm as two people who need help. Restorative justice focuses on the person who was harmed and the person who caused harm to provide them the necessary support required to heal, allowing the hammer to amend themselves and make right their wrongs, repairing the harm, and restoring the lives of harmed individuals to create a hopeful future.

In a restorative justice process, the person who was harmed and the person who caused harm will come face to face with one another. This meeting could take place months after the crime occurs or many years later. In this meeting, the person who was harm and the person who caused harm are assisted by a trained professional. This meeting allows the person who was harmed to express their feelings, thoughts, questions, and emotions. It enables the person who caused harm to explain, answer, and express their feelings and thoughts. This process allows the person who was harmed to move in the direction of healing; giving the person who was harmed any form of insight as to why a crime occurred to them gives them their peace back. The person who was harmed no longer has to wonder and find all the answers to their questions. These questions no longer haunt them and consume their lives; the person who caused takes responsibility for the crime and understands themselves, leading them to commit this crime and restitution. After the restorative justice process, the person who caused harm is less likely to offend and commit serious crimes than if they had gone through the traditional criminal justice process. The person who was harmed is no longer in fear that the person who caused them harm will re-offend. Vam Camp and Wemmers (2013) found that dialogue was considered an essential step to closure by most regardless of whether or not it had resulted in knowing the whole truth or having the person who

caused harm recognize responsibility. It referred to the need to use the opportunity to communicate with the person who caused harm as a tool to heal, even if it might have seemed difficult to do at first. The dialogue was empowering. To some, coming face to face with the person who caused them harm will never be a good idea. Some people wish to never see the person who caused them harm ever again in their life, while others believe it is the only solution for them to move forward with their life. There are several reasons why a person who was harmed would like to come face to face with the person who caused them harm. A person who was harmed in a restorative justice process seeks information. A person who was harmed wants the person who caused them harm to know the harm they have caused; their healing process begins through this discussion. The restorative justice profession does not happen from one day to another. The person who caused harm and the person who was harmed need to prepare with a facilitator to ensure that they can meet. Coming face with the person who caused harm or coming face with the person who was harmed is not an easy thing to do. So the person who caused harm and the person who was harm must be emotionally prepared for a meeting like this.

Indigenous Practices

Restorative justice is gaining more attention from people advocating and pushing for the restorative justice process. Restorative justice practices did not come from modern times (Johnstone, 2013). Surprisingly, restorative justice was built from pre-modern traditions such as Navajo Peacemaking. Like restorative justice, Navajo Peacemaking represents a natural, authentic form of justice. A meeting between the person who was harmed and the person who caused harm is formed to discuss their feelings and resolution. A plan of action is created for restitution from the wrongdoer to the person who was harmed. This leads to a solution and reduces the rate of recidivism.

Peacemaking deliberately incorporates cultural tools and normative judgments. 'Because violence is socially constructed . . . the solutions to such violence must be found in the stories and values of the participants' cultures' (Coker, 2006). The cultural tools available to Navajo Peacemakers are particularly well suited to support women's safety and independent worth. Navajo creation stories and journey narratives underscore the importance of harmony, notably gender harmony. Coker (2006) states that stories offer the potential to describe Navajo masculinity in ways that support gender-egalitarian relations and transform how the batterer and his family understand his battering behavior.

Peacemaking is one of several initiatives designed to reform Navajo law to meet Navajo people's needs better. Other measures include the requirement that judges' speak both Navajo and English, and have some knowledge of Navajo culture and tradition' and the statutory provision that makes incarceration an 'extraordinary measure' to be 'imposed only as a last alternative. The most impressive recent legislative change occurred in 2000 when the Navajo legislature eliminated fines and incarceration for over 60 offenses, requiring courts to use Peacemaking, security bonds, and community service (Coker, 2006). Navajo people are a primary example of a community that has decided to utilize restorative justice as an effective tool in their community.

Criminal Justice System

In the 1900s, rehabilitation was the primary criminal justice value. McAlinden (2011) believes that efforts such as rehabilitation measures should be designed to effect changes in the behavior of a convicted person in the interests of his happiness, health, and satisfaction and the welfare of social defense. However, judges and board of correction decided to disregard this idea and didn't make much effort to encourage precipitation in the prison system. The lack of action to rehabilitative a person who caused harm results in no change in the criminal justice system. Values

have been implemented in the criminal justice system to impose the rehabilitate deal in the criminal justice system. During the 1970s, retribution gained prominence and remains the primary core value in the criminal justice system (McAlinden, 2011). Retribution is from the belief of "an eye for an eye," the idea that a criminal should receive the same punishment for their crimes. The court also looks at the criminal's past criminal history to determine their sentence.

Deterrence has been a core value in the criminal justice system. It purposes kit to put fear in the criminal and the public to reduce crime. In efforts to make people fear being punished by the law, there are significant efforts to increase the severity of the punishment. Under the "three strikes law," minor crimes were treated as high-level crimes. Some people were sentenced to the highest degree of homicides and murder for petty crimes. Studies have shown that the severity of punishment has resulted be an ineffective form of deterrence. Deterrence, though throughout time, has been seen as an irrelevant core value of the criminal justice system since the kit has been proven to be ineffective (McAlinden, 2011). Incapacitation has been a core value that has been implemented in the criminal justice system for years. Incapacitation is built on the logic that no harm can be done by removing a criminal from the street. Although this is true, it's only a temporary solution. Incapacitation is the paramount value in criminal justice that has been efficiently enforced to keep the public safe. However, not all crimes are equipped to be punished by being incarcerated. Incapacitation does not deal with the underlying issues of the criminal. If anything, it makes everything worst. Incapacitation should not be a core value we should strive for. Many people can agree that our current core values need to be redefined and that our criminal justice system needs to be reformed.

Rizer (2018) seeks to determine how our American Criminal Justice reveals our values and who we are. He challenges his readers to think and be open about new options about our criminal justice system, specifically about our criminal justice core values. Rizer (2018) argues that our criminal justice core values, rehabilitation, retribution, deterrence, and incapacitation, are not getting us anywhere in the criminal justice system. These values continue to fail our most accurate notions of justice, respect human dignity, and restoring public safety. These values are not the answers to seeing a positive difference in our society. Rizer (2018) presents historical facts and data throughout his article to change people's perspectives on the core values that have been implemented in our system for years. Rizer (2018) offers revised core values that better represent us and lead us to a better criminal justice system.

We have learned that punishment should be in the form of taking something away from someone. As a kid, when you would misbehave in a classroom, you would get something taken away, usually your recess. The Criminal Justice System believes that taking away a person's freedom is the best solution. The Criminal justice system has been built on punishment; our greatest resolution on any form of crime has been incarceration. Our criminal justice system is made on the idea of being "tough on crime" and an "eye for an eye" mentality. We have lived and believed in this form of punishment for many years. We believe that this is the best form of justice being served. However, we can't say that incarcerating a person who has caused harm is not justice for all. Justice has a different meaning to each person who was harmed. To some people, justice may be incarceration, but to others, incarceration may not do them any justice at all. Restorative justice allows the person who was harmed to have their complete, meaningful form of justice. The criminal justice system needs to make the person who was harmed needs their priority.

Many person who was harmed will allow the crime done to them to consume their lives, which reflects their unhealed wounds. This can lead the person who was harmed to self-destruction and pain for many years after the crime. Criminal justice does not cater to the person who was harmed needs and the efforts to ensure that a crime never happens again. Many people would agree that incarceration is not the best solution for the person who caused harm. We can also agree that incarceration does not decrease crime and rehabilitate people. Restorative justice will not fix all our problems in the criminal justice system. However, it can help us start building an effective method.

Punishment in the criminal justice system has been utilized to deter crime. It allows the public to know that you will get punished to the full degree if you commit a crime. If this ideology is correct, then the United States should be the safest country in the world. We are locking up the felons to allow other prisoners to know the consequence and to enable the felony to not commit the same crime. In a sense, incarceration should be stopping or deterring felons and deterring the criminals once they are released. If this is the case, then why is it not working? It is not practical because incarceration doesn't provide the person who caused harm with the resources to receive help and understand the crime.

People in prison are angry at how the system harmed them and not for the harm that they have caused. Incarceration doesn't allow the person who caused harm to understand their feelings. It allows them to ignore the harm they have committed continuously. They don't have to look at anyone in the face and see the damage they have caused. Incineration only allows the people who caused harm to stay in their heads with the idea of how they are being harmed, and they don't feel accountable. Punishment doesn't deter crime or rehabilitate individuals. If anything, it feeds our problem. Many people will wonder how a restorative justice process will

prevent crime? How will the public fear that they will commit a crime that the punishment they will receive is sitting in a circle singing kumbaya? Punishment means revenge. We seek revenge to feel the same pain and hurt when we punish someone. Time after time, we have seen that punishment does nothing for the person who was harmed. If restorative justice existed and was the leading form of punishment and resolution to crime, we would know it would deter crime.

Mass Incarceration

The United States is the leading Country to incarcerate people in the world. The United incarcerates 20% of the people in the world of our 5% population, which means roughly 2.1 million people behind bars in the Country (Leipold, 2019). According to Leipold, 2019, the United States prison population increased from 200,000 to 1.6 million between 1972 and 2009. This leads to overcrowded prisons that cause the United States many complex problems. Incarceration has always been the United States' first and only approach as a form of punishment. The Criminal Justice system is built and continues to grow from the perception of viewing people for their crimes, stereotyping people who caused harmed, racisms, and unwillingness to treat prisoners' mental health. When a system is built from this, it is impossible to rehabilitate prisoners. The United States, for its entire existence, has seen punishment as its primary resolution.

The United States points the finger at the prisoners to our problem with incarceration. But, the criminal justice system never decides to look at the issue as to why so many people end up in jail. The Criminal Justice system needs to find other effective forms of punishment. We have heard the phrase "tough on crimes" for many years. This phrase was advocated and built from the idea that the harsher and longer the punishment will lead to recidivism. Prisons don't hold rehabilitation resources that will transform an inmate's life for the better. If anything,

prisons increase the chances of a person who caused harm to cause harm again. Leipid (2019) states that half of the federal prisoners will be re-arrested after being released, and more than 80% of state prisoners will be arrested again.

Nigeria is suffering tremendously due to the overcrowding of prisons.

Nigeria utilizes traditional criminal justice system corrective measures in correctional facilities that keep the people who caused harm institutionalized. Nnam (2017) argues that Nigeria should not cling to the punitive approaches of the criminal justice system that is based on the ideology of separating the person who caused harm from the person who was harmed and the entire society. Nnam (2017) states that criminal justice administrators should advocate for the numerous opportunities Restorative Justice offers to reduce the numbers of people who caused harm to Nigerian prisons. In efforts to emphasize that restorative justice is the resolution to our problems.

Sered (2021) states that people have this false perception that restorative justice is about forgiveness and treating the person who caused harm as your own. However, restorative justice is about pragmatism. Forgiveness does not need to occur for restorative justice to work. However, restorative justice can come with forgiveness. The person who was harmed hold anger towards their harmer, and while holding this emotion, they cannot forgive. Restorative justice allows the person who was harmed to let go of some of the feelings that the person who was harmed has bottled inside them. Sered (2021) states that for years we have only been given two options, "criminal justice or nothing." Our lack of options has people who were harmed either doing nothing about the harm that has been done to them or receiving justice on the terms of the criminal justice system.

Restorative Justice Process

Several values shape restorative justice, which makes it distinctive from any other. Restorative justice takes an approach that focuses on justice and resolution. The restorative justice system values are participation, respect, honesty, accountability, interconnectedness, vulnerability, empowerment, and hope (*Restorative Justice Values and Processes*, 2003). Throughout the restorative justice process, these are the core values being focused on and targeted every step of the way. For restorative justice to be possible, the person who caused harm, the person who was harmed, and any other participants have come together willingly to participate in the restorative justice process. Each person involved in the restorative justice process has something to contribute to their meeting. The restorative justice process occurs in a safe environment. Throughout the process, all participants have to be respectful to one another. Honesty is crucial for restorative justice to be effective. All participants have to be truthful in the process. Without the truth, the restorative justice process would be pointless. All people gather in this meeting, to tell the truth, good or bad. The entire story between all participants unravels before their eyes.

The facts, questions, answers, comments, etc., all contribute to the healing of everyone. Vulnerability is a powerful emotion that occurs in the restorative justice process. The participants have to be and will be in a vulnerable place when in the circle. The person who caused harm will be accepting their wrongs in front of the person they hurt, and the person who was harmed will be speaking about the pain that the person who caused then harm inflicted. At times, the person who was harmed and the person who caused harm form a connection throughout this process. A connection that allows them to be understanding and compassionate for one another.

The connection between the person who caused harm and the person who was harmed allows them to see each other as one. The person who was harmed is not sitting in front of the person who caused them harm but another human being. This connection is so powerful because it allows the person who was harmed and the person who caused harm to move past the roles of bad and good. Accountability is an essential core value for the person who caused harm. The person who caused harm is allowed to take full responsibility for their actions. There is no hiding or filtering the truth but taking full responsibility for their actions. The overall restorative justice process is empowering for the person who caused harm and the person who was harmed. Empowerment for the person who caused harm to have the courage to tell all truth, and empowerment allows the person who was harmed to regain their power. Finally, hope is needed for the restorative justice process. Our community can remain hopeful that after the process, the person who caused harm will continue their effort to change and expect that the person who was harmed will move forward with their life. These values need to be implemented throughout to fulfill the intentions and purpose of restorative justice successfully.

"Understanding" and "compassionate" are the words used to describe a woman's (Shonna Robinson's) harmer (Zehr, 2015). A woman lost her mother at the hands of the man sitting across from her. She expected him to be an individual who lacked remorse and evil, but he turned out to be the exact opposite. When she saw this man, who took her mother's life, she did not see a monster but a human. A human was no different from her but who made a wrong decision. A Restorative justice process brings humanity back to the table. When a vicious crime occurs to someone, we like to believe, and we think that the hammer is far from humane. However, a person who caused harm is like you and me who has battles to fight. After meeting with the person who caused her harm, she states that her "emptiness was filled, and anger was diminished" (Zehr, 2015). The

women did not go into the restorative justice process having revenge in mind. She went in wanting to leave the restorative justice process with her questions answered and have some sense of closure.

Although we believe that revenge will give us the satisfaction that we feel that we deserve and allow us to move, revenge brings nothing. Every person who has been harmed has the right to desire revenge. And they are at no fault for thinking like this. However, revenge brings more anger and hatred to your heart. Forgiveness does not have to happen in the restorative justice process. However, forgiveness allows us to release the hate and anger in our hearts to move forward. Forgiveness becomes more manageable when you see the person who has harmed you feel remorseful and want to make a difference in their behavior. In most cases, the person who caused harm feels as much pain as the person who was harmed.

In the restorative justice process, the person who caused harm is being taken away from their ability to deny what they have done, deprived of accountability. They no longer will be able to hide from the person who they harmed; they will be held accountable for the harm that they have caused. A restorative justice professional states that restorative justice is the hardest thing a person who caused harm will do. The person who caused harm has to come face to face to the person that they hurt and explain and accept their wrong in front of the people they have harmed and their loved ones. Many people will argue that Restorative justice is a slap on the hand of the person who caused harm since we are not taking away their freedom and locking them up in cages. However, I am arguing that sometimes it is not always the right solution to keep the person who caused harm away from society as their punishment.

In many cases, this will encourage and lead the person who caused harm in the wrong direction and make him worst when returning to the community. A person who caused harm, in

most cases, needs to go through a restorative justice process to face the people they hurt the most. This allows the person who caused harm to show the person that they harmed the remorse and effort they're doing to be a changed individual.

Effectiveness of Restorative Justice

There is no form of healing when we seek revenge or want another to suffer. This person will never heal from their trauma. If a person does not recover from their past trauma, they will continue to carry this weight on their shoulders, negatively affecting their life. I have always believed that justice is served when the person who was harmed feels that justice has been served. Not when the court or the judge decides. Every person who has been harmed has a different story. We don't know the pain and the hurt that a person who was harmed has endured, "we can only imagine." In Restorative Justice, the person who was harmed are not a case number but a person who is deserving of the justice that brings them closure.

As stated by Johnstone (2013), "victims rarely experience justice when traditional punitive methods deal with the case." Moving towards restorative justice can give the person who was harmed the answers to their questions. Restorative justice gives the person who was harmed the closure they need and allows healing to occur. Bergseth and Bouffard (2013) found that RJ programs found an average reduction of 8% in the reoffending rate of those who participated in programs involving restorative features (e.g., restitution, community service) relative to those who participated in programs that did not include such features.

Restorative practices have been used in juvenile justice settings with success. McMahon and Pederson (2020), in a *meta*-analysis of restorative justice diversion programs, found that 15 out of 21 programs reviewed had positive impacts, including reduced recidivism. The Restorative Community Conferencing (RCC) program in Alameda County, California, a youth

diversion program that supports youth in facilitated dialogues with the people they harmed, has found that only 18.4% of RCC youth committed a subsequent act of delinquency, compared to 32.1% of youth in the traditional juvenile legal system. A systematic review of police-initiated juvenile diversion programs noted that restorative justice diversion programs might be effective because they model conflict resolution skills for youth.

RJ conferences provides the person who was harmed with the potential to get more of what they want from criminal justice. Research over the past 20 years is remarkably consistent in its findings that the people who have been harmed want most is different from what the formal justice system assumes is essential for them too (McMahon and Pederson, 2020). The person who was harmed consistently report that they value the opportunity for meaningful participation in their cases highly, with the chance to ask the important questions that they want information about the way their cases are being dealt with. They want to be treated respectfully and fairly. Strang et al. (2006) research program has reports that the person who was harmed consistently say that emotional restoration is what they desire most from their "justice" experience and what they so rarely find in the formal justice system. The restorative justice research consistently reports a preference for apology over money or vengeance (Strang et al., 2006).

Most people who were harmed of a wide range of crimes focus far more on the person who caused harm statements of understanding the harm they caused and expressions of remorse for having caused it. We have repeatedly observed that when a person who caused bring up compensation first, the person who was harmed usually divert that issue until a complete and emotionally painful discussion of the harm has been completed. Even when that discussion is finished, the person who was harmed tends to focus much more on how future crime can be prevented than on their material reparation by addressing a person who caused harm

rehabilitation and reintegration. All of this, in turn, places the person who was harmed in the morally powerful position of shaping the future about the past moral weakness of the offender. (Strang etc., 2006).

The Compassion Prison Project is a non-profit organization whose mission is to transform prisons and communities through compassionate action. A Grammy award-winning producer, Horton decided to film a short documentary with the help of the Compassion Prison Project; *Step inside the Circle*. This documentary examines the pervasiveness of childhood trauma, one of the key factors behind America's high levels of incarceration." Step inside the Circle" demonstrated that every prisoner in that Circle has something in common. Each prisoner was able to relate to one another, allowing the prisoners to realize that they all came from similar backgrounds that contributed to them ending up in prison. Our childhood has a massive effect on the people that we become. We all don't start from the same playing field. Some children are raised in unsupported, traumatic, and violent homes. At the same time, other children have never experienced such pain. Each person has different battles that they need to fight and overcome. The sad thing about every person that is in prison is that they didn't win their battles. As stated by Horstman states that she, too, was not on a good path and could have easily been one of the prisoners (*Step Inside the Circle*, 2021). However, she was able to get a pass for being white. Horstman got a second chance due to the color of her skin. While other inmates never stood a chance in fighting their battles. For many reasons such as lack of support, knowledge, resources, etc.

But most importantly, many of them never received a helping hand. Although it does not excuse an inmate's behavior, it allows us to understand. Understand that we could be like them if

our paths had been different; Horstman is giving inmates a helping hand that they need to change and get a second chance.

Restorative Justice reduces the person who was harmed unforgiving motivations and anger and increases their positive responses to the person who caused harm more than retributive Justice. In terms of physiology, forgiveness was associated with less negative and aroused response patterns, and justice benefits emerged only in the absence of forgiveness. These results further suggest that even if the pursuit of justice is impeded, the person who was harmed can take action that may hold some subjective and physiological benefits for themselves. (Witvliet et al., 2018). Restorative Justice is a helpful resource that can be brought into prisons.

As stated in the *Communities for Restorative Justice: Success Data*, restorative justice "puts the power back in the hands of those affected by crime." Having the hammer faces their crime and agreeing to some form of restitution will allow the person who caused harm to understand and accomplish restitution. Looking at the data provided by the "Communities for Restorative Justice," restorative justice has shown to be a better alternative in all categories. There is a 9% less likely chance of the person who caused harm will re-offending in a restorative justice process than in the criminal justice process. The person who was harm satisfaction with the process is 22% higher than the criminal justice process(*Communities for Restorative Justice: Success Data*, n.d.).

Allowing the person who was harm walk away feeling satisfied once the process of over is very important. Restorative justice gives the person who was harmed justice has been served based on what they felt is appropriate. People who were harmed that have participated in a restorative justice process are 13% less likely to live in fear of being harmed again. The person who was

harm has come face to face with the person who caused them harm and has had a meeting where they don't see him as a criminal or a "monster" but as a human. There is a 9% higher chance that the person who caused harm will leave satisfied with a restorative justice process than with the criminal justice process. There is a 23% difference in restitution between restorative justice and criminal justice. There is a significantly higher chance for a person who caused harm to restore and amend themselves. Data has proven a significant difference between criminal justice and restorative justice. Restorative justice has proven to impact the person who caused harm and the person who was harmed lives positively. The restorative justice process is a positive change in the criminal justice system. Form of punishment and resolution to crime, we would see that would deter crime. As stated by Van Camp and Wemmers (2013) a restorative approach moves beyond interactional justice to providing care. Consequently, the restorative approach was not just a decision-making or dispute resolution process; it was also a source for support and empowerment

Restorative Justice Outside Criminal Justice

Restorative justice is not a practice that can only be utilized in the criminal justice system. Restorative justice is a practice that can be used in our everyday lives. It can be used at home with our families, at schools with our peers, and at work with our coworkers. It is an effective resource to have restorative programs in schools concerned with relationship building and repairing the harm caused by acts of misbehavior, delinquency, and crime rather than with punishment that encourages recidivism (Payne & Welch, 2015). Restorative justice gives students individualized solutions that allows the person who was harmed to receive closure and the offending students to repair the harm caused by the misbehavior. According to Payne & Welch (2015), studies have shown restorative programs and a better alternative than traditional school

punishment, which is often associated with various negative academic outcomes and may increase the probability of student deviance and delinquency

Methods

My research focuses on how a restorative justice course (CRJU-410) shifts students' ideas about justice, punishment, and personal beliefs. Answering the question, Does a restorative justice course taught from a restorative justice perspective change how students think about crime and justice? By answering my research question, I hope my readers have further knowledge about Restorative Justice and encourage my readers and audience to view restorative justice as a resolution in our criminal justice system.

In the Spring of 2021, I decided to enroll in CRJU-410. CRJU-410 is an introduction course of restorative justice. It teaches students the applications of restorative justice, values inherent in restorative justice, the purpose of restorative justice, the various types of restorative justice, and the theoretical and practical underpinnings of restorative justice. By the end of the semester, students will develop an appreciation for restorative justice and restorative practices in CRJU-410. CRJU-410 was taught by Dr. Alissa Ackerman. Dr. Ackerman is a Criminal Justice Professor at California State University, Fullerton. She has published several books, including *Healing from Sexual Violence: the case for Vicarious Restorative Justice*. She is a Restorative Justice Facilitator & Trainer. In class, we learned about restorative justice from a professor who is an expert in restorative justice and has years of experience as a facilitator.

For my research study, I decided to create a pre-survey and post-survey that was given to students enrolled in CRJU 410 for the Spring of 2021. The pre-survey and post-survey were identical to compare the student's responses from the beginning to the end of the semester. The

pre-survey and post-survey consisted of students being asked questions that range from the scale from never to always, from strongly agree to disagree strongly, and almost always false of me to almost always true of me. My questions were created from the themes of empathy, punishment orientation, forgiveness, and social connectedness. By having these questions in scale form, I can understand and analyze the data by levels.

The pros of my quantitative data are that statistical analysis is straightforward and factual when presented. I was easily able to compare my findings and precisely calculate the difference in the responses from the pre and post-survey. If my data is calculated correctly, it is very reliable information that can be trusted. This data allowed me to determine how students changed in the themes of empathy, punishment orientation, forgiveness, and social connectedness. Although my data can be very trustworthy if appropriately done, it can be uncertain if not done correctly. I can only hope that all students put effort and honestly when responding to my survey, but I can't be sure they all did. I could not observe when this survey was taken or calculate each student's effort in the survey. Therefore, my data can cause some doubt.

In the same survey, they were asked open-ended questions that dealt with the themes of understanding, redemption, and connection. There were asked questions such as Would you instead understand someone, or would you rather have them understand you? What are your thoughts on redemption? If possible, please explain if you have ever felt connected with a stranger. What was that experience like? These open-ended questions allowed students to explain their responses' reasoning, thoughts, and opinion.

My research study also consists of Students Questionnaire responses about their experiences in CRJU-410. This qualitative is essential to illustrate students' honest thoughts about

the class. The pros of my qualitative data are that I can read firsthand students' opinions, thoughts, and ideas related to restorative justice. I can better understand students' views, ideas, and opinions through their responses. It can add honest and vulnerable meaning to my project that quantitative data cannot. The con of my qualitative data is that I interpret students' responses to what I think they meant, which means that my data could be very subjective. To prevent this, ensure that I am only being as factual as possible and never biased to align their responses to my thoughts and opinions.

My N ranges between 34-38 of the same participants, meaning that I was able to get several inputs from the same questions being asked. Students for the pre-survey and post-survey were asked the same questions making my data consistent and dependable. The independent variable in my study is the restorative justice course. This is the variable that will result in my dependent variable from changing. Restorative justice course is the "influencer" or "because" of my dependent variable, while the dependent variable is students' thoughts on crime and justice.

The dependent variable is the "effect" or changes that "depends" on the independent variable. I think there are exogenous variables that I should beware of in my study. A student can be influenced by the criminal justice course (independent) to think differently about crime and justice (dependent). However, the criminal justice course is not the only variable that can influence the dependent variable. The amount of time a student spends on CRJU 410 material will influence their thoughts on the knowledge they have gained about restorative justice. Another variable to consider is the student's capability to understand the material they are being taught. All students will have a different understanding of restorative justice based on how they can comprehend the material. The effort that students spent on learning about restorative justice will influence the dependent variable. I also need to consider students who have done further research outside of

CRJU 410 class material about restorative justice throughout the semester. These are all exogenous variables that I need to consider when deciding the true impact of a restorative justice course alone on student thoughts about crime and justice.

Data & Data Analysis

Table 1.1: DEMOGRAPHICS

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sex		
Female	68.4	66.0
Male	31.6	34.0
Race/Ethnicity	(n=57)	(n=52)
Hispanic/Latino	56.1	55.8
Asian	15.8	11.5
Black	3.5	5.8
White	14.0	13.5
Mixed Race	10.5	13.5
Religion	(n=58)	(n=53)
Catholic	40.0	39.6
Christian	23.3	26.4
Buddhist	5.0	0.0
Islam	0.0	3.8
None	31.7	30.4

Table 1.1 numbers in the pre and post column represent the percentage for the corresponding demographics.

Table 1.2 DEMOGRAPHICS

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Age (Mean)	23.32	23.9

Table 1.2 numbers in the pre and post column represent the average age.

Table 2: EMPATHY SCALE

EMPATHY SCALE	Pre	Post	Difference
Other people's misfortunes do not disturb me a great deal.	1.29	1.71	0.42
It upsets me to see someone being treated disrespectfully.	3.72	3.85	0.13
I remain unaffected when someone close to me is happy.	1.24	1.02	0.22
I find that I am "in tune" with other people's moods.	2.68	2.98	0.30
I do not feel sympathy for people who cause their own serious illnesses.	1.25	1.09	0.16
I am not really interested in how other people feel.	0.70	0.57	0.13
I get a strong urge to help when I see someone who is upset.	3.20	3.32	0.12
When I see someone being taken advantage of, I feel kind of protective towards them.	3.35	3.55	0.20

The Empathy Scale ranged from Never (0) to always (4). The numbers in the pre and post column represent the average response. The numbers in the difference column represent the amount of change between the pre and post survey responses.

The empathy scales shows that students were more empathetic after taking the CRJU-410 course.

Table 3: FORGIVENESS SCALE

FORGIVENESS SCALE	Pre	Post	Difference
It is really hard for me to accept myself once I've messed up.	3.94	3.71	0.23
I don't stop criticizing myself for negative things I've felt, thought, said, or done.	4.29	3.67	0.62
I continue to punish a person who has done something that I think is wrong.	2.55	2.04	0.51
With time I am understanding of others for the mistakes they've made.	5.48	5.83	0.35
I continue to be hard on others who have hurt me.	3.07	2.54	0.53
If others mistreat me, I continue to think badly of them.	3.74	2.69	1.05
When someone disappoints me, I can eventually move past it	5.40	5.19	0.21
With time I can be understanding of bad circumstances in my life.	5.60	5.92	0.32

The Forgiveness Scale ranged from Almost Always False of Me (1) to Almost Always True of Me (7). The numbers in the pre and post column represent the average response. The numbers in the difference column represent the amount of change between the pre and post survey responses.

The forgiveness scale emphasizes that students from the statements above were more forgiving towards other and themselves after having taken CRJU-410. CRJU-410 didn't go into depth about forgiveness because you don't need forgiveness in a restorative justice process. Although, forgiveness may come with the restorative justice process. I think students were more forgiving at the end of the semester because we were trying to understand why a person who caused harm decided to commit a crime.

Table 4: PUNISHMENT ORIENTATION SCALE

PUNISHMENT ORIENTATION SCALE	Pre	Post	Difference
Punishment is necessary because it sends the message to the community that crime will not be tolerated.	3.30	2.60	0.694
It is more important to punish a guilty person because he deserves it than it is to punish him to benefit society.	3.04	2.37	0.57
The goal of punishment should be to give the guilty person what he deserves.	3.14	2.47	0.67
Criminals are bad people and deserve punishment.	2.32	1.87	0.45
When a person commits the crime, he upsets the balance of justice. The only way to make this right is to punish him accordingly.	3.02	2.50	0.52
If a crime has a low detection rate (i.e. it is difficult to catch criminals who commit this particular crime), we should punish those who are caught harshly to prevent others from thinking they can get away with it.	2.67	1.96	0.71

Even if society would benefit greatly from punishing an innocent person, he should not be punished because he does not deserve it.	4.20	3.71	0.49
Criminals are in prison because they deserve to be there.	2.37	1.86	0.51

The Social Punishment Orientation Scale ranged from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5). The numbers in the pre and post column represent the average response. The numbers in the difference column represent the amount of change between the pre and post survey responses.

The Social Punishment Orientation Scale proves that students are less supportive of punishing people who have caused harm from Criminal Justice characteristics. Throughout the semester we were taught that punishment should not be our only goal when a person causes harm. Our goal should be to understand why the person who caused harm decided to commit a crime and through the restorative justice process is able to find a solution that fits with the person who was harmed and the person who caused harm needs.

Table 5: SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS SCALE

SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS SCALE	Pre	Post	Difference
I feel comfortable in the presence of strangers.	3.36	3.94	0.58
I fit in well in new situations.	3.86	4.02	0.16
I feel disconnected from the world around me.	2.71	2.31	0.40
Even around people I know, I don't feel that I really belong.	2.20	2.43	0.23
I see people as friendly and approachable.	3.80	4.02	0.22
I feel understood by the people I know.	4.52	4.67	0.15
I feel distant from people.	2.88	2.67	0.21

I am able to relate to my peers.	4.36	4.82	0.46
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The Social Connectedness Scale ranged from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (6). The numbers in the pre and post column represent the average response. The numbers in the difference column represent the amount of change between the pre and post survey responses.

The social connectedness scale illustrates that students at the end of the semester felt that are able to relate to one and other than compared to the beginning of the semester. CRJU-410 gave us the opportunity for our voices to be heard in a safe environment. An environment that you were surrounded by peers who were understanding and compassionate towards one another. I think all students social connectedness improved tremendously after taking the course.

Open-Ended Questions

In the survey students were asked open-ended questions to give students the opportunity to explain their reasoning, thoughts, and opinion behind their responses. Students were asked questions that dealt with redemption, understanding, and connection. Table 6.1 list the responses to the questions from the pre-survey. While Table 6.2 list the responses to the questions from the post survey.

Table 6.1: PRE-TEST OPEN-ENDED QUESTIONS & RESPONSES

Questions	Pre-Test Responses
Understanding	
Would you rather understand someone, or would you rather have them understand you?	<i>BOTH, frame of reference is important for everyone to know depending on the situation. for example, knowing how people would like to be addressed, or approached, or perhaps keeping in mind what others have been through to ensure certain environments</i>
	<i>I think I would rather understand someone. I think I guess, selfishly, it gives me peace of mind understanding someone. Understanding someone's</i>

	<i>actions allows me to process what they are saying and doing better.</i>
Redemption	
What are your thoughts on redemption?	<i>Same thoughts as second chances. I am a big example of redemption. I turned my life.. I am no longer a high school drop out and no longer a criminal.</i>
	<i>Redemption can be good or bad depending on who or what is trying to obtain forgiveness or a reestablished social status.</i>
Connection	
If possible, please explain if you have ever felt connected with a stranger. What was that experience like	<i>I have never felt a true connection with a stranger. However, through a pleasant encounter I have had good experiences with strangers.</i>
	<i>Not that I can recall at this time.</i>

Table 6.2: POST-TEST OPEN-ENDED QUESTIONS & RESPONSES

Questions	Post-Test Responses
Understanding	
Would you rather understand someone, or would you rather have them understand you?	<i>I would rather understand someone because most of the time not everything will be about me. I want to be able to understand their beliefs and feelings so that I can empathize and see from their point of view (kinda like being in their shoes).</i>
	<i>I would rather understand someone because I want to be able to help them and make an impact in their life.</i>
Redemption	
What are your thoughts on redemption?	<i>I think that redemption is very possible and that there are many instances where people can redeem themselves if they want to put that effort and work into it. I think that redemption only works if you yourself have hope and the mindset to work for it. As for redemption for others, I say that is possible to hope for others to redeem themselves but it does have to show.</i>
	<i>hat someone is capable of redeeming themselves, which I think happens more often than not. A lot of people have a tendency to dismiss that.</i>
Connection	

<p>If possible, please explain if you have ever felt connected with a stranger. What was that experience like</p>	<p><i>I feel like sometimes I connect with strangers without even talking. I am always looking around, curious of other people, and I just like to watch. Sometimes when I am quite and alone, just watching I see things that others do that remind me of me, or make me happy. at times like these I feel like are when I connect with strangers, because without even speaking to them, I can feel their joys by just watching.</i></p>
	<p><i>I felt connected with a stranger because we have shared similar experiences and struggles. I have connected with a stranger because we have both shared pain. I never imagined I could have a connection with someone I just met, but it taught me that we all share similar emotions in this world it's just a matter of being open to those around us.</i></p>

There wasn't much data that could be compared between the post and survey responses.

We could see that students' responses to questions from the themes of understanding, redemption and understanding slightly changed. It is difficult to be certain that it was the same students' responses to the questions since all responses are anonymous. However, this data is beneficial in understanding students responses through their explanation.

Student Opinion Questionnaire

At the end of the semester, students were asked to complete a student opinion questionnaire. The purpose of the questionnaire is for students to give their anonymous, honest feedback about the instructor, course material, and their overall thoughts about the class. This is helpful in understanding what students felt about CRJU 410. These are some student's responses on their experience with Professor Ackerman in CRJU 410:

- *“The strongest features of this course were the class discussions, Professor Ackerman truly encourages the class to participate in class discussions, during this time the class will go*

over the weekly reading material and reflect on important topics. Professor Ackerman is truly connected with every student, there is always communication with one another.”

- *“She is patient. Everyone is willing to participate during lectures and makes us feel heard. She doesn’t pressure us to do anything. She understands us probably more than our parents do and i love that about her. She had given me so much trust that literally i can tell her anything and not feel ashamed.”*
- *“Alissa is the best professor I have yet had in CSUF. Having taken this and other courses with her made me feel valued and important as a student. I think that she is very positive and professional at what she knows, so it was very helpful to have her guide us through this class. I felt so supported and I feel that I learned so much from this class and it was not nearly as stressful as other have been. We need more classes like these for CJ majors. This class made you learn and think about CJ topics in a whole new way, but at the same time it was easy to apply these themes to our personal lives.”*

These are some responses that students had on their takeaway from CRJU 410:

- *“As the class went on I actually found myself changing/ evolving the way i thought. I also love how Professor Ackerman created such a safe space for us to share and learn it makes the class so much more interesting and fun”*
- *“Amazing class, I learned a lot that I can take outside with me and apply it to my life or potential career.”*
- *“The strongest features of the class were how engaged the whole class was in learning and communicating about restorative justice. The class was very stimulating, and it helped give us skills that would be very beneficial for us to use in the future. I also felt like our professor*

made the environment open and was always available to communicate and continually communicated with us on any updates, and I really appreciated it.”

- *“Dr. Ackerman first spent an adequate amount of time making sure the class understood why it is important to understand a survivor needs as opposed to just basing their needs on laws. I feel that much of what I have learned in this specific class will be use when I become a law enforcement employee or pursue any other career within criminal justice. What I also really enjoyed learning in this class is that restorative justice can be applied in other areas, not just within the current legal system.”*

These responses illustrate that students learned and enjoyed the class. Students expressed that they felt supportive and safe in the environment that Dr. Alissa Ackerman created. This class gave students the opportunity to be vulnerable and feel connected with their peers. This class did not only teach us about how restorative justice can be applied in the criminal justice system but as well in our ever day lives. Overall, a great class that influenced our lives.

Conclusion

The data I collected illustrates that learning about restorative justice in a sixteen-week course through lectures, discussions, and activities will influence students' perception on empathy, forgiveness, punishment, and social connectedness. Allowing me to conclude that a restorative justice course taught from a restorative justice perspective change how students think about crime and justice. Further research can be done with a larger sample of students who are not criminal justice majors. I think it would be very beneficial to see if a population with no prior knowledge of restorative justice is influenced by a class. This type of study would be able to speak for all people in general.

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References

- Bergseth, & Bouffard, J. A. (2013). Examining the Effectiveness of a Restorative Justice Program for Various Types of Juvenile Offenders. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 57(9), 1054–1075.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X12453551>
- Coker. (2006). Restorative justice, Navajo Peacemaking and domestic violence. *Theoretical Criminology*, 10(1), 67–85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362480606059983>
- Communities for Restorative Justice: Success Data*. (n.d.). Razia’s Ray of Hope.
<https://www.c4rj.org/>
- Johnstone, G. (2013). *Restorative Justice: Ideas, Values, Debates*. London: Routledge.
- Zehr, H., Amstutz, L. S., MacRae, A., & Pranis, K. (2015). *The big book of restorative justice: Four classic justice & peacebuilding books in one volume*. New York, NY: Good Books.
- Leipold, A. D. (2019). Is mass incarceration inevitable. *American Criminal Law Review*, 56(4), 1579-1620
- Macpherson U Nnam. (2017). Responding to the Problem of Prison Overcrowding in Nigeria through Restorative Justice: A Challenge to the Traditional Criminal Justice System. *International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences*, 12(1), 177–.
- McAlinden, A. (2011). 'Transforming justice': Challenges for restorative justice in an era of punishment-based corrections. *Contemporary Justice Review: CJR*, 14(4), 383-406.
- McMahon, & Pederson, S. (2020). “Love and compassion not found Elsewhere”: A Photovoice exploration of restorative justice and nonviolent communication in a community-based

juvenile justice diversion program. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 117, 105306–.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2020.105306>

Payne, & Welch, K. (2015). Restorative Justice in Schools: The Influence of Race on Restorative Discipline. *Youth & Society*, 47(4), 539–564.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X12473125>

Restorative Justice Values and Processes. (2003, June). Restorative Justice Network.

<http://restorativejustice.org/10fulltext/restorativejusticenetwork.pdf>

Rizer, A. (2018, September 20). All Call for a Revised Set of Values in Criminal Justice.

Retrieved May 12, 2021, from

https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5b4cc00c710699c57a454b25/t/5ba3b58e352f5302573b0339/1537455502633/A+Call+for+a+Revised+Set+of+ValuesArthur+Rizer_Final.pdf

Sered, D. (2021). *Until We Reckon: Violence, Mass Incarceration, and a Road to Repair*

(Reprint ed.). The New Press.

Step Inside the Circle. (2021, June 28). Compassion Prison Project.

<https://compassionprisonproject.org/the-documentaries/>

Strang, Sherman, L., Angel, C. M., Woods, D. J., Bennett, S., Newbury-Birch, D., & Inkpen, N.

(2006). Victim Evaluations of Face-to-Face Restorative Justice Conferences: A Quasi-Experimental Analysis. *Journal of Social Issues*, 62(2), 281–306.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.2006.00451.x>

Van Camp, & Wemmers, J.-A. (2013). Victim satisfaction with restorative justice: More than simply procedural justice. *International Review of Victimology*, 19(2), 117–143.

Witvliet, Worthington, E. L., Root, L. M., Sato, A. F., Ludwig, T. E., & Exline, J. J. (2008). Retributive justice, restorative justice, and forgiveness: An experimental psychophysiology analysis. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 44(1), 10–25.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2007.01.009>

Zehr, H., MacRae, A., Pranis, K., & Amstutz, L. S. (2015). *The Big Book of Restorative Justice: Four Classic Justice & Peacebuilding Books in One Volume (Justice and Peacebuilding)*. Good Books.